

Prof. Nina F. Thornhill's Research Assistant 1999 to 2002

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Abstract: As a collaborator of Prof. Thornhill at Imperial College London from 1999 to 2002 I produced work on closed-loop identification with a quantizer and reconstructed time series from quantized measurements.

Keywords: Closed-loop identification, quantizer, reconstruction of time series.

1. INTRODUCTION

Prof Nina Thornhill kindly offered me a 3-year Research Assistant position at CPSE, Imperial College London (from Jan. 1999 to Jan. 2002).

My part-time PhD was registered at UCL (also under the supervision of Prof Nina Thornhill).

During these 3 years, I learned a lot from Prof Nina Thornhill. Even today, I have the copy of my PhD Thesis commented by Prof Thornhill.

This also reminds me to treat my PhD students seriously.

Many thanks to Prof Nina Thornhill for her kind academic guidance.

During this period, we published three papers.

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